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A Comparative study of the effect of zinc oxide and silver nanoparticles against antibiotic-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

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Abstract

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is an opportunistic Gram-negative bacterium that causes serious infections in immunocompromised patients and is known for its high capacity to develop resistance to multiple antibiotics, making infections difficult to treat. The study aimed to investigate the prevalence of multiple antibiotic-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* species that cause many diseases, and to estimate the impact of nanoparticles on them and their use as alternatives or adjuncts to antibiotic treatment. A total of 182 clinical samples were collected, including urinary tract infections, wound swabs, pus, burns, and tonsillitis, from patients arriving at Al-Kindi Hospital in Baghdad between March to September 2024. Twenty-nine strains of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (16%) were identified based on morphological and cultural characteristics, biochemical tests, and the APi20E test. These strains were tested for their sensitivity to 10 types of antibiotics. The species showed high resistance to Ampicillin and Amoxicillin (100%), and the least resistance to Ciprofloxacin (35%). Nine strains with high resistance to antibiotics were selected, and the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined against the antibiotics under study. In addition, some nanoparticles of different sizes (Ag20, 90nm, ZnO20, 30, 50~150, nm. The results showed that the MIC for Ag20, 90nm was 650-2600 µg/ml, while for ZnO20nm, the MIC values ranged between 81.25 -2600 µg/ml, while the MIC for ZnO30, 50~150nm was between 325- 2600 (µg/ml). The synergistic effect between antibiotics and nanomaterials showed high effectiveness in inhibiting the growth of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Keywords: Multi-resistant to antibiotics; *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*; Zinc oxide and silver nanoparticles

1. Introduction

Nanoparticles are a distinct class of fine materials that can be produced with dimensions ranging from 1 to 100 nanometers. The small size and dimensions of these materials allow them to behave differently from conventional large sized materials with dimensions greater than 100 nanometers. This means that nanoparticles have electrical and magnetic properties that differ significantly from larger particles of the same compounds [1]. Metallic nanoparticles can be obtained by biological, physical, and chemical methods, as several types of bacteria and fungi have the ability to produce metal nanoparticles with antimicrobial properties [2]. It has been known since ancient times that silver and its compounds have various effects against microorganisms and viruses. This is due to the small size of its particles, less than 5 nanometers, which increases their surface area and thus leads to a tendency to migrate to the outer surface of the nanoparticles, increasing their chemical activity and increasing the production of reactive oxygen species, including the formation of free radicals. [3] Silver nanoparticles also have the ability to cross living membranes, such as skin affected by eczema or burns, and reach the bloodstream, leading to increased oxidative stress, the production of cytokines, inflammation, and ultimately cell death [4]. Zinc oxide nanoparticles are among the most popular metal oxides, possessing numerous properties, most notably semiconductor properties and antibacterial activity, which has attracted significant interest as an antibacterial treatment [5]. They have stronger antibacterial activity than zinc oxide, due to the significantly increased surface area of the particles. Zinc oxide nanoparticles rival other metal oxide

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nanoparticles in their antibacterial activity against a wide range of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria [6]. Pathogenic bacteria characterized by multidrug resistance and possessing plasmids have become a major problem for humans, particularly as these bacteria are resistant to a number of antibiotics and can continue to grow in the body despite antibiotic treatment [7]. Adding antibiotics to nanoparticles has shown synergistic effects against bacteria. Using the particles alone has shown a 40% inhibition of their growth, and the percentage increased significantly with the addition of antibiotics [8]. Accordingly, the study aimed to investigate the prevalence of multiple antibiotic-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* species that cause many diseases, and to estimate the impact of nanoparticles on them and their use as alternatives or adjuncts to antibiotic treatment.

2. Material and Methods

A total of 182 samples were collected from patients attending Al-Kindi Hospital in Baghdad city during the period from March to September 2024. The samples included urine, wound swabs, pus, burns, and tonsillitis. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was isolated and identified from the different samples according to [9,10] based on morphological, cultural, and biochemical characteristics, and the API-20E system prepared by BioMerieux according to its specifications [11].

Antibiotic sensitivity testing was performed using the disc diffusion method. Ten antibiotics were used: Ampicillin (AM/10 µg), Amoxicillin (AX/25 µg), Erythromycin (E/15 µg), Ciprofloxacin (CIP/5 µg), Chloramphenicol (C/30 µg), Cefotaxime (CTX/30 µg), Nitrofurantoin (NF/300 µg), Co-Trimoxazole (COT/25 µg), Doxycycline (DO/30µg), Ceftriaxone (CRO/30µg). Using solid Mueller-Hunton medium, the media were incubated at 37°C for 18 hours. The results were compared with international measurements, as stated in [12]. The broth dilution method was used for quantitative assessment to demonstrate the effectiveness of antibiotics and nanoparticles. A 96-well microtiter plate method was used, and the assay was conducted according to [13,14] as follows:

- 100 microliters of Mueller-Hunton broth were added to each well.
- 100 microliters of the previously prepared antibody at a concentration of 1024 µg/ml were added to well 1 of row A. The antibody was mixed by vibrating up and down for 6-8 minutes, resulting in a double concentration of 512 µg/ml. • Transfer 100 microliters from well 1 to well 2 and mix with the same movement. Thus, the diluent concentration became 256 µg/mL. • The process was repeated until reaching well 10, after which 100 microliters were withdrawn and discarded, resulting in a concentration of (512, 256, 128, 64, 32, 16, 8, 4, 2, 1) µg/ml.
- 5 microliters of 24-hour-old bacterial suspension were added to each well.
- Only broth and bacterial suspension were added to well 11, creating a positive control.
- Well 12 became a negative control, containing only broth and antibody.
- Another antibody was added to row B, and so on for the other rows.
- The plate was covered and incubated at 37°C for 18-24 hours.
- Visually check for growth, and then note the MIC (minimum inhibitory concentration) of the antibody by observing the turbidity of the medium.

As for the nanoparticles, the same method was used, using a concentration of 5200 µg/ml, previously prepared in hole 1 of row A. This resulted in concentrations of (2600, 1300, 650, 325, 162.5, 81.25, 40.6, 20.3, 10.15, 5.07) µg/ml. The synergistic effect of silver particles and zinc oxide, individually with antibiotics was estimated by adding 50 microliters of the particles at their minimum inhibitory concentration with 50 microliters of antibiotics at their inhibitory concentration to 5 mm diameter holes after inoculating the surfaces of the plates with the pure species under study. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours, and the diameters of inhibition around the holes were measured (in mm). The process was repeated twice, and the average was taken [15].

3. Results and Discussion

182 clinical samples were collected from patients, including urinary tract infections, wound swabs, pus, burns, and tonsillitis. Twenty-nine strains of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (16%) were identified based on morphological and cultural characteristics, biochemical tests, and the API20E test. Figure (1) shows the percentage of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolated from different clinical sources, with 13 isolates from burns dominating (45%).

Figure 1 The percentage of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolated from different clinical sources

The sensitivity of the isolated bacteria to 10 antibiotics was studied by measuring the zone of inhibition diameter and comparing the results with what was reported in [16]. The results in Figure (2) showed that there was a variation in the resistance of the isolates under study to the antibiotics used. The bacteria showed high resistance to the antibiotics Ampicillin and Amoxicillin at 100%, consistent with many researchers [17]. They were followed by the antibiotics Nitrofurantoin, Co-Trimoxazole, Ceftriaxone, and Erythromycin at 88%, 84%, 77%, and 71%, respectively. The results also showed high resistance to some antibiotics, including Cefotaxime and Doxycycline at 67% and 61%, respectively. This percentage is considered normal rate to the indiscriminate use of antibiotics. This result is consistent with [18], where a high percentage of resistance to the antibiotic Cefotaxime was found among *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolates. The resistant to Chloramphenicol at a moderate rate of 55%, while the lowest resistance was to Ciprofloxacin 35%. Ciprofloxacin has shown a broad effect against Gram-negative bacteria, as recorded by [19], as it inhibits the activity of the DNA gyrase enzyme [20].

Figure 2 Resistance rates of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolates to the antibiotics under study

9 strains with high resistance to antibiotics were selected and the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined against the antibiotics under study. As shown in Table 1, the breakpoint described by [12] was adopted as the basis for calculating the response. The results showed that all isolates showed complete resistance to all antibiotics and gave high MIC values compared to the breakpoint, with the exception of the sensitivity of all isolates to the antibiotics Cefotaxime and Ceftriaxone, and 8 isolates were sensitive to Nitrofurantoin, where the MIC values ranged between 2-64 µg/ml, except for one isolate that was resistant, with an MIC value of 128 µg/ml.

Table 1 Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of different antibiotics against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolates

Isolate number	MIC									
	AM	AX	NF	COT	CRO	E	CTX	DO	C	CIP
P1	512	256	128	256	64	16	2	16	64	4
P2	128	256	64	64	32	128	16	32	32	16
P3	512	128	32	8	16	256	8	4	128	32
P4	256	128	16	64	8	64	16	32	64	4
P5	128	128	8	16	4	64	8	8	8	2
P6	512	256	16	64	2	128	64	32	32	32
P7	128	512	4	32	8	16	64	128	128	4
P8	128	512	32	8	32	256	32	64	32	8
P9	512	256	2	32	16	128	8	16	8	32

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) for silver nanoparticles (Ag-NP) with a size of 20 and 90 nm on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolates is shown in Table 2. It was between 650 - 2600 µg/ml, indicating that *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolates are more resistant and require a higher concentration of silver nanoparticles to affect bacterial growth. These results are similar to what was reported by [21]. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) for zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO-NP) with a size of 20 nm on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolates was between 81.25- 2600 µg/ml, while the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) for zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO-NP) with a size of 30 nm was between 325- 1300 µg/ml while the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) for zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO-NP) with a size of 50~150nm was between 325-2600 µg/ml. The antibiographical activity of zinc oxide nanoparticles against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* bacteria increases with the decrease in particle size [22].

Table 2 Minimum inhibitory values (MIC) of different nanoparticles against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolates

Isolate number	MIC				
	ZnO20nm	ZnO30nm	ZnO50~150nm	Ag20nm	Ag90nm
P1	1300	650	1300	2600	650
P2	1300	1300	650	2600	2600
P3	650	1300	650	1300	650
P4	650	1300	1300	1300	2600
P5	81.25	1300	650	650	650
P6	2600	1300	2600	325	650
P7	1300	325	650	2600	2600
P8	325	650	325	1300	1300
P9	650	650	325	2600	625

Table (3) shows the effect of the relationship between antibiotics and nanoparticles on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* bacteria, where the antibiotics (E, CIP, CTX, DO, CRO) showed an increase in the average diameter of the inhibition zone when mixed with the nanoparticles used in the study and their different sizes. The study [23] showed the emergence of a synergistic effect when the combination of silver nanoparticles and the antibiotic chloramphenicol against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* bacteria is inconsistent with [24]. However, it is consistent with [25], which stated that antibiotics showed a synergistic effect with nano zinc oxide against bacteria producing extended-spectrum beta-lactamase enzymes. The combination of nano zinc oxide and antibiotics increases the permeability of the cell membrane, thus leading to protein leakage from the bacterial membrane.

Table 3 Effect of the combination of antibiotics and nanoparticles on the species *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

Antibiotics	Antibiotic effect alone	Antimicrobial effect with nanoparticles					The effect of nanoparticles alone				
		ZnO2 0nm	ZnO3 0nm	ZnO50~1 50nm	Ag20 nm	Ag90 nm	ZnO2 0nm	ZnO3 0nm	ZnO50~1 50nm	Ag20 nm	Ag90 nm
AM	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
AX	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
NF	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
COT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CRO	10	13	10	11	7	8	0	0	0	0	0
E	8	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CTX	9	9	11	10	11	11	0	0	0	0	0
DO	8	7	8	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0
C	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CIP	14	17	16	14	18	17	0	0	0	0	0

4. Conclusion

We conclude from this study that nano zinc oxide is more effective against antibiotic-resistant bacteria than silver nanoparticles. The bacterial isolates were resistant to several groups of antibiotics, including penicillins and cephalosporins, while they were sensitive to ciprofloxacin. The synergistic effect of the antibiotics and nanoparticles used in the study against the bacterial isolates varied. Ciprofloxacin, Ceftriaxone, and Cefotaxime, when combined with the nanoparticles used in the study, had the highest effect against the bacterial isolates.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There are no conflicts of interest for any of the authors.

Statement of informed consent

This study was done with the consent of the patients or the parents.

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